

Circle packing inside a regular pentagon: supplemental material

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular pentagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular pentagon that we have found using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 200$. Although we cannot claim that these configurations correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, they provide good lower bounds to the packing fraction. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader should refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular pentagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 200$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $2 \leq N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceed by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is large:

configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular pentagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.437152698242	0.505009863813	41	0.120982726955	0.79292869341
3	0.389795792433	0.602280894881	42	0.119848963425	0.797115755296
4	0.354680462504	0.664872028015	43	0.118421345534	0.796768171019
5	0.340440645254	0.765695954932	44	0.117257562843	0.799351771064
6	0.309016994371	0.757041202668	45	0.115792923917	0.797223502406
7	0.277511095117	0.712298912009	46	0.114685668831	0.799428585597
8	0.2575418245	0.701114681674	47	0.113728619203	0.80323186512
9	0.243640224399	0.705901377803	48	0.112997340346	0.809806426252
10	0.230721507966	0.703363296033	49	0.111299134462	0.802016295533
11	0.22433359334	0.731450345446	50	0.110419276505	0.805495905631
12	0.217384640521	0.749277161806	51	0.108971323158	0.800199292506
13	0.207999994722	0.743144963271	52	0.107852410315	0.799220458881
14	0.202386816023	0.757697772154	53	0.106722676369	0.797614101983
15	0.197735768366	0.77493498733	54	0.105895776586	0.800118988953
16	0.191785609135	0.77759874971	55	0.104863207018	0.799120918109
17	0.183126736787	0.753279195582	56	0.104252744674	0.804204614084
18	0.178473321196	0.757569801809	57	0.103187535998	0.801923385362
19	0.17344190433	0.755205607498	58	0.10243566142	0.804144107685
20	0.169279411749	0.757254419213	59	0.101468332217	0.802632228934
21	0.16540401864	0.759127889229	60	0.100739761056	0.804556636832
22	0.161673301786	0.759806203277	61	0.0998596971384	0.803736816959
23	0.158923367389	0.767550381307	62	0.0991937627378	0.806053665934
24	0.15602729845	0.771997613946	63	0.0984549105547	0.806898395454
25	0.153122210789	0.774497337031	64	0.0978344217881	0.80940685412
26	0.1506833367	0.780022883175	65	0.0970134326327	0.808315000086
27	0.148137584795	0.782884729566	66	0.0962561099644	0.807986466941
28	0.145444423784	0.782628611099	67	0.09578509126	0.812220928717
29	0.143333013135	0.787216154548	68	0.0950777443077	0.812213475287
30	0.141698173815	0.795890460898	69	0.0944389054714	0.813119767721
31	0.13861636221	0.787035327241	70	0.0937363375517	0.812676198074
32	0.135793611068	0.779672455391	71	0.0930018278117	0.811418406722
33	0.134134799538	0.78451347486	72	0.0924058778363	0.812335118938
34	0.131960534659	0.782295061275	73	0.0918565854644	0.813854920939
35	0.130170592942	0.783605271723	74	0.091081045227	0.811131504665
36	0.128214082074	0.781947317559	75	0.0905264255332	0.812111287467
37	0.126679668746	0.78454724318	76	0.0898834987058	0.811291766759
38	0.125056798044	0.785238789165	77	0.0892757648044	0.810889024851
39	0.124185689922	0.794714714624	78	0.0887536700901	0.811840630353
40	0.12241379178	0.791998265961	79	0.0881556080319	0.811204815762

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular pentagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.087759391831	0.814105587246	121	0.0718010222006	0.824233312419
81	0.0872565104928	0.81486232602	122	0.0715041299022	0.824186737531
82	0.0865310148143	0.811261721868	123	0.0712362118458	0.824727134218
83	0.0860625021869	0.812287122267	124	0.0709242148263	0.824165245806
84	0.0855822398407	0.812924329854	125	0.0706630972793	0.824705498653
85	0.0851056402032	0.813465521534	126	0.0704116265611	0.825396907757
86	0.084693623818	0.815085975933	127	0.0701989474179	0.826929451716
87	0.0843535589172	0.817955377428	128	0.0697848961031	0.823638009995
88	0.083957834448	0.819612676803	129	0.0697294642818	0.828754512293
89	0.0833739837475	0.817437678079	130	0.0693873262533	0.827003212373
90	0.082914295828	0.817532226762	131	0.0690713947035	0.825793167091
91	0.0824866750791	0.818111555841	132	0.0688265127464	0.826207248553
92	0.0820971093956	0.819307816012	133	0.068547486146	0.825730343978
93	0.0816048537424	0.818311149587	134	0.0682613501372	0.825007857139
94	0.0812260274241	0.819448791189	135	0.0680079892403	0.825006130782
95	0.0807677809398	0.81884828872	136	0.0677177989024	0.824039658738
96	0.0803010402663	0.81793183973	137	0.0675457015746	0.825884925983
97	0.0799432325913	0.819103315124	138	0.067317086304	0.826291423522
98	0.0796051028128	0.820562053498	139	0.0670430549016	0.825516825215
99	0.0793030868925	0.82265722908	140	0.066827568773	0.826119545035
100	0.0788467193251	0.821430442804	141	0.0665564063455	0.825282013937
101	0.0783787898256	0.819826626975	142	0.0663016274486	0.824784062598
102	0.0780381068902	0.820761848712	143	0.0661045388481	0.825661692969
103	0.0776315433259	0.820195162226	144	0.0658772653687	0.825728275263
104	0.0771688296386	0.818315363892	145	0.0656941851992	0.8268474696
105	0.076787199063	0.818032371564	146	0.0654879089562	0.827329749791
106	0.076515935681	0.819998750451	147	0.0652887206323	0.827936806977
107	0.0761493933789	0.819823215144	148	0.0650514793831	0.827522115497
108	0.0757549916494	0.818935699023	149	0.064918082337	0.829700155886
109	0.0754834293612	0.820603343254	150	0.0646486130727	0.828348751582
110	0.0751311054474	0.820419135761	151	0.0644267326805	0.828157044074
111	0.074877167713	0.822290616349	152	0.0642592010605	0.829311656459
112	0.0744931460514	0.821209932271	153	0.0640189434282	0.828537126494
113	0.0742788979979	0.823783114583	154	0.0637974364371	0.82819139739
114	0.0739647126086	0.824057541156	155	0.0637402524221	0.832075615049
115	0.0735997268181	0.823102239934	156	0.0635231871694	0.831749784001
116	0.0733244470321	0.824060544078	157	0.0632128787567	0.828923264271
117	0.0729788406379	0.823347781702	158	0.063027535531	0.82931835438
118	0.0727088839195	0.82425293517	159	0.0628777907431	0.830606280988
119	0.0723926962814	0.824024272546	160	0.0626222787867	0.829051015677
120	0.0721257841515	0.824832719449	161	0.0624831768661	0.830530564275

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular pentagon for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0622925003784	0.83059646807	182	0.0588619842379	0.833191292577
163	0.0620873941563	0.830229208168	183	0.0585850517736	0.829904776802
164	0.0618627300274	0.829288322341	184	0.0583265144115	0.827091217125
165	0.0617022921344	0.830022906489	185	0.0583374282549	0.831897513953
166	0.0615024224081	0.829652201674	186	0.0580880528132	0.829258859209
167	0.0613334097422	0.830069063865	187	0.0579423076457	0.829538831154
168	0.0611978591428	0.831352638703	188	0.057740118418	0.828164725116
169	0.0609842978851	0.830474495255	189	0.0576088627705	0.828788939976
170	0.0607834988013	0.829896341844	190	0.0575391355295	0.831158412508
171	0.0606174299872	0.830222860983	191	0.0574440891168	0.832774848813
172	0.0604787816992	0.831262240555	192	0.0573996791813	0.835841051488
173	0.0603081499324	0.831383982938	193	0.0572509984479	0.835847364996
174	0.0601325405276	0.831327011935	194	0.0569661864056	0.831839543362
175	0.0599255650424	0.830358933831	195	0.0568366889047	0.832330269615
176	0.059760210955	0.830501555204	196	0.0567181445172	0.833112478674
177	0.0595791654046	0.830167324209	197	0.0565920801816	0.833644866601
178	0.059476265188	0.831976231361	198	0.056326448677	0.830029388101
179	0.0592851923882	0.831283263034	199	0.0561958920715	0.830358726871
180	0.0591180030623	0.831219178297	200	0.0560374757046	0.829832923312
181	0.0589986327502	0.832465047515			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of a pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

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References

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